

РАЗДЕЛ. ТЕХНИЧЕСКИЕ НАУКИ

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**ИЗМЕНЕНИЕ КОНЦЕНТРАЦИИ ЖИДКОСТЕЙ
РАЗНОЙ ПЛОТНОСТИ ПО ДЛИНЕ ТЕЧЕНИЯ**

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Аннотация: В статье рассматриваются альтернативные инженерные методы использовались для борьбы с засолением в условиях нехватки воды. Исходя из требований по опреснению верхнего слоя подземных вод, орошению этого слоя в промывном режиме, нахождению влагоудерживающих параметров дренажа и другим методам. Кроме того, осуществляется путем удаления загрязненных вод, математического моделирования изменения уровня подземных вод и принятия аналитических или численных решений этих моделей и их применения.

Ключевые слова: фильтрационный уровень воды обусловленного просачиванием из русла в грунт, плотность грунта, дебит, пористость, метод конечных разностей, коэффициент размерности граничного условия

**CHANGES IN THE CONCENTRATION OF LIQUIDS WITH
DIFFERENT DENSITIES ALONG THE FLOW LENGTH**

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Annotation: In this article researches the alternative engineering methods against salinity have been used in water-scarce conditions. Based on the requirements for desalination of the upper layer of underground water, irrigation of this layer in washing mode, finding moisture-retaining parameters of drainage and other methods were found and used. However, currently available methods cannot provide optimal drainage parameters and cannot remove mineral salts from deep groundwater. Because the concentration against the salinity of irrigated lands itself was adapted to the critical depth during this period. In addition, it is carried out by removing contaminated water, mathematical modeling of changes in the level of underground water and taking analytical or numerical solutions of these models and applying them.

Keywords: seepage water level due to seepage from the channel into the soil, soil density, flow rate, porosity, finite difference method, boundary condition dimension factor

Introduction. Irrigation issues are one of the most urgent issues in the world. The shortage of irrigation water requires finding a way to use waste collector water as well. It is known that the concentration of collector water can be different. The concentration of the mixture changes as a result of the addition of collector water to the river water [1-2]. Discharged collector water does not immediately disperse among the canal water. Therefore, it is necessary to know the rules and conditions for such mixed waters to be suitable for irrigation. The mixing of the collector waters with the channel waters takes place by the diffusion process, that is, the mixing process of waters with different densities takes place [3].

Main part. This process allows to write the mathematical model of the reservoir water thrown into the open pit through the diffusion process [4]. We write the homogeneous diffusion equation in open channels with the same cross-section for the mixing of canal and collector waters of different densities, and it is written as follows [5-6]:

$$\rho \frac{\partial C}{\partial t} + \vartheta \rho \frac{\partial C}{\partial x} = \frac{\partial}{\partial x} \left(D \rho \frac{\partial C}{\partial x} \right) \quad (1)$$

We solve equation (1) based on the following initial and boundary conditions:

initial conditions:

$$C(x, t)|_{t=t_0} = C_0, \tag{2}$$

boundary conditions:

$$\mu h \frac{\partial C}{\partial x} \Big|_{x=0} = -(C - C_0), \tag{3}$$

$$\mu h \frac{\partial C}{\partial x} \Big|_{x=L} = (C - C_0), \tag{4}$$

here C – concentration;

$\mathcal{G}$ – filtration rate component;

D – diffusion coefficient;

h – canal water level;

μ – channel water loss coefficient;

C_0 – initial concentration values;

ρ – the density of the inflowing collector water.

This is to solve the problem

$$C^* = \frac{C}{C_0}, \quad x^* = \frac{x}{L}, \quad D^* = \frac{D}{D_0}, \quad \tau = \frac{D_0}{L^2} t, \quad \rho^* = \frac{\rho}{\rho_0}, \quad h^* = \frac{h}{h_0}, \quad \mathcal{G}^* = \frac{\mathcal{G}}{\mathcal{G}_0}.$$

we introduce dimensionless quantities.

Then (1) – (4) are expressed as follows:

$$\rho^* \frac{\partial C^*}{\partial \tau} = \frac{\partial}{\partial x^*} (D^* \rho^* \frac{\partial C^*}{\partial x^*}) - \xi \mathcal{G}^* \rho^* \frac{\partial C^*}{\partial x^*}, \tag{5}$$

here $\xi = \frac{\mathcal{G}_0 L}{D_0}$.

$$C|_{\tau=\tau_0} = C_0, \tag{6}$$

$$\frac{\mu h_0 C_0}{L} h^* \frac{\partial C^*}{\partial x^*} \Big|_{x^*=0} = -(C_0 C^* - C_0), \tag{7}$$

$$\frac{\mu h_0 C_0}{L} h^* \frac{\partial C^*}{\partial x^*} \Big|_{x^*=1} = (C_0 C^* - C_0), \tag{8}$$

For the sake of simplification, we omit the sign "*" in equation (5) and boundary conditions (7) – (8) and write as follows:

$$\rho \frac{\partial C}{\partial \tau} = \frac{\partial}{\partial x} (D\rho \frac{\partial C}{\partial x}) - \xi \vartheta \rho \frac{\partial C}{\partial x}, \quad (9)$$

$$C|_{\tau=\tau_0} = C_0, \quad (10)$$

$$\frac{\mu h_0 C_0}{L} h \frac{\partial C}{\partial x} \Big|_{x=0} = -(C_0 C - C_0), \quad (11)$$

$$\frac{\mu h_0 C_0}{L} h \frac{\partial C}{\partial x} \Big|_{x=1} = (C_0 C - C_0), \quad (12)$$

Solving the differential equation (9),(10)–(12) analytically on the basis of initial and boundary conditions is considered complicated (difficult). Therefore, we solve problems (9) – (12) using the finite difference method. To do this, we insert the following mesh into the area:

$$\omega_{\Delta x, \Delta \tau} = \{x = i \Delta x; i = 0, 1, 2, \dots, I; t_j = j \Delta \tau; j = 1, 2, \dots, N\}$$

We approximate equation (9) in the form of an implicit finite difference scheme using a grid:

$$\rho_i \frac{C_i^{j+1} - C_i^j}{\Delta \tau} = \frac{\rho_{i-0.5} D_{i-0.5} C_{i-1}^{j+1} - (\rho_{i-0.5} D_{i-0.5} + \rho_{i+0.5} D_{i+0.5}) C_i^{j+1} + \rho_{i+0.5} D_{i+0.5} C_{i+1}^{j+1}}{\Delta x^2} - \frac{\xi}{2\Delta x} (2(|\vartheta \rho_i| - \vartheta \rho_i) C_i^{j+1} - (|\vartheta \rho_i| - \vartheta \rho_i) C_{i-1}^{j+1} - (|\vartheta \rho_i| - \vartheta \rho_i) C_{i+1}^{j+1}), \quad (13)$$

We can simplify the equation (14) and express it in the following form:

$$\begin{aligned} & \left(\frac{\rho_{i-0.5} D_{i-0.5}}{\Delta x^2} + \frac{\xi}{2\Delta x} (|\vartheta \rho_i| - \vartheta \rho_i) \right) C_{i-1}^{j+1} - \\ & - \left(\frac{\rho_{i-0.5} D_{i-0.5} + \rho_{i+0.5} D_{i+0.5}}{\Delta x^2} + \frac{\xi}{\Delta x} (|\vartheta \rho_i| - \vartheta \rho_i) + \frac{\rho_i}{\Delta \tau} \right) C_i^{j+1} + \\ & + \left(\frac{\rho_{i+0.5} D_{i+0.5}}{\Delta x^2} + \frac{\xi}{2\Delta x} (|\vartheta \rho_i| - \vartheta \rho_i) \right) C_{i+1}^{j+1} = - \frac{\rho_i}{\Delta \tau} C_i^j, \end{aligned} \quad (14)$$

We express the finite difference equation (14) in the form of a system of three-diagonal linear algebraic equations as follows:

$$a_i C_{i-1}^{j+1} - b_i C_i^{j+1} + c_i C_{i+1}^{j+1} = -d_i, \quad (15)$$

here

$$a_i = \frac{\rho_{i-0.5} D_{i-0.5}}{\Delta x^2} + \frac{\xi}{2\Delta x} (|\mathcal{G}\rho_i| - \mathcal{G}\rho_i),$$

$$b_i = \frac{(\rho_{i-0.5} D_{i-0.5} + \rho_{i+0.5} D_{i+0.5})}{\Delta x^2} + \frac{\xi}{\Delta x} (|\mathcal{G}\rho_i| - \mathcal{G}\rho_i) + \frac{\rho_i}{\Delta \tau},$$

$$c_i = \frac{\rho_{i+0.5} D_{i+0.5}}{\Delta x^2} + \frac{\xi}{2\Delta x} (|\mathcal{G}\rho_i| - \mathcal{G}\rho_i), d_i = \frac{\rho_i}{\Delta \tau} C_i^j,$$

We solve the obtained system of equations (15) for the sought variables by the driving method [7-8]. We find the solutions at the interior points of the grid using the following recurrent formulas:

$$C_i^{j+1} = \alpha_{i+1} C_{i+1}^{j+1} + \beta_{i+1}, \tag{16}$$

Here, the coefficients α_i, β_i – are found by the following equation (in this $b_i - a_i \alpha_i \neq 0, b_i^1 - a_i^1 \alpha_i^1 \neq 0$).

$$\alpha_{i+1} = \frac{c_i}{b_i - a_i \alpha_i}, \beta_{i+1} = \frac{d_i + a_i \beta_i}{b_i - a_i \alpha_i}, \quad i = 1, 2, \dots, N - 1. \tag{17}$$

We approximate the boundary conditions (11)-(12) in high-order accuracy using $\omega_{\Delta x, \Delta \tau}$ mesh

$$\frac{\mu h_0 C_0}{L} h_1 \cdot \frac{C_0^{j+1} - 4C_1^{j+1} + 3C_2^{j+1}}{2\Delta x} = -(C_0 C_1^{j+1} - C_0), \tag{18}$$

$$\frac{\mu h_0 C_0}{L} h_l \cdot \frac{-3C_{l-1}^{j+1} + 4C_l^{j+1} - C_{l+1}^{j+1}}{2\Delta x} = (C_0 C_l^{j+1} - C_0), \tag{19}$$

α_i, β_i the values of α_1 and β_1 are needed to calculate the (17) relation. We find these values as follows.

At $i = 1$, (15) is from the system of equations

$$C_2^{j+1} = \frac{b_1}{c_1} C_1^{j+1} - \frac{a_1}{c_1} C_0^{j+1} - \frac{d_1}{c_1}, \tag{20}$$

we will have equality, (18) – from the boundary condition we create the following equality with respect to C_2^{j+1} :

$$C_2^{j+1} = \frac{4\mu h_0 C_0 h_1 - 2\Delta x L C_0}{3\mu h_0 C_0 h_1} C_1^{j+1} - \frac{1}{3} C_0^{j+1} + \frac{2\Delta x L}{3\mu h_0 h_1}, \quad (21)$$

Comparing equations (20) and (21), we find the value of C_0^{j+1} :

$$C_0^{j+1} = \left(\frac{4\mu h_0 C_0 h_1 c_1 - 2\Delta x L C_0}{\mu h_0 C_0 h_1 (c_1 - 3a_1)} - \frac{3b_1}{c_1 - 3a_1} \right) C_1^{j+1} + \frac{2\Delta x L c_1}{\mu h_0 h_1 (c_1 - 3a_1)} + \frac{3d_1}{c_1 - 3a_1}, \quad (22)$$

((16) assuming $i = 0$ in the recurrent expression

$$C_0^{j+1} = \alpha_1 C_1^{j+1} + \beta_1. \quad (23)$$

we get the equality and by comparing the equalities (22), (23) we find the coefficients α_1 and β_1 :

$$\alpha_1 = \frac{4\mu h_0 C_0 h_1 c_1 - 2\Delta x L C_0}{\mu h_0 C_0 h_1 (c_1 - 3a_1)} - \frac{3b_1}{c_1 - 3a_1},$$

$$\beta_1 = \frac{2\Delta x L c_1}{\mu h_0 h_1 (c_1 - 3a_1)} + \frac{3d_1}{c_1 - 3a_1}.$$

In order to find the solution (16) according to the identified coefficients α_{i+1} , β_{i+1} ($i = N - 1$) by the recurrent formula, the limit value of C_I^{j+1} must be known. For this, assuming $i = I$ in (15),

$$C_{I+1}^{j+1} = -\frac{a_I}{c_I} C_{I-1}^{j+1} + \frac{b_I}{c_I} C_I^{j+1} - \frac{d_I}{c_I}, \quad (24)$$

we have the equality, we find h_{I+1}^{j+1} from the boundary condition (19):

$$C_{I+1}^{j+1} = \frac{2\Delta x L - 4\mu h_0 h_I}{\mu h_0 h_I} C_I^{j+1} + 3C_{I-1}^{j+1} - \frac{2\Delta x L}{\mu h_0 h_I}, \quad (25)$$

Equating the right-hand side of equations (24) and (25), we get

C_{I-1}^{j+1} :

$$C_{I-1}^{j+1} = \left(\frac{b_I}{3c_I + a_I} - \frac{2\Delta x L c_I - 4\mu h_0 h_I c_I}{\mu h_0 h_I (3c_I + a_I)} \right) C_I^{j+1} - \frac{d_I}{3c_I + a_I} + \frac{2\Delta x L c_I}{\mu h_0 h_I (3c_I + a_I)}, \quad (26)$$

(16) assuming $i = I - 1$ in the recurrent formula

$$C_{I-1}^{j+1} = \alpha_I C_I^{j+1} + \beta_I. \quad (27)$$

we will have equality.

Conclusion. In conclusion, it can be said that

1. From equations (26) and (27), we find the limit value of C_I^{j+1} .
2. We find the values of $C_{I-1}^j, C_{I-2}^j, \dots, C_1^j$ using the progonka method.

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